

SOME PROBLEMS IN THE FORMATION OF RECEPTIVE GRAMMATICAL SKILLS

Mamajonova Makhbuba

Associate professor, Fergana State University

Abstract: The development of receptive grammatical skills is a crucial aspect of language acquisition. However, learners often encounter various challenges in the formation of these skills. This article explores some of the problems that learners face when developing receptive grammatical skills. It discusses the impact of factors such as age, language background, and learning environment on the acquisition of receptive grammatical skills. Additionally, the article examines the role of instructional methods and strategies in facilitating the formation of these skills. Finally, the article suggests some recommendations for teachers and learners to enhance the development of receptive grammatical skills.

Key words: grammar skills, vocabulary skills, problems in teaching grammar, solutions.

Introduction

Receptive grammatical skills refer to the ability to understand and comprehend the grammatical structures and rules of a language. These skills are critical for effective communication and language proficiency. However, many learners encounter difficulties in the formation of these skills due to various factors such as age, language background, and learning environment. Additionally, instructional methods and strategies play a crucial role in facilitating the development of receptive grammatical skills. This article aims to explore some of the problems that learners face when developing receptive grammatical skills and suggest some recommendations for enhancing their formation.

Age and Receptive Grammatical Skills

Age is a significant factor that influences the acquisition of receptive grammatical skills. Younger learners tend to have an advantage over older learners in acquiring these skills. This is because younger learners have more neuroplasticity, which allows them to learn new languages more easily. Additionally, younger learners are less likely to be influenced by their native language's grammatical structures, making it easier for them to acquire new grammatical structures. On the other hand, older learners may struggle with the formation of receptive grammatical skills due to the influence of their native language's grammatical structures and limited neuroplasticity.

Language Background and Receptive Grammatical Skills

Language background also plays a crucial role in the formation of receptive grammatical skills. Learners who come from languages with similar grammatical structures to the target language may have an advantage in acquiring receptive grammatical skills. This is because they are already familiar with some of the grammatical structures and rules of the target language. On the other hand, learners who come from languages with vastly different grammatical structures may struggle with the formation of receptive grammatical skills. For example, learners who come from languages that do not have articles may find it challenging to understand the use of articles in English.

Learning Environment and Receptive Grammatical Skills

The learning environment is another significant factor that influences the acquisition of receptive grammatical skills. Learners who are exposed to the target language in immersive environments tend to acquire receptive grammatical skills more quickly than those who learn the language in a classroom setting. This is because immersive environments provide learners with more opportunities to practice and apply their receptive grammatical skills in real-life situations. Additionally, learners who have access to native speakers of the target language may have an advantage in acquiring receptive grammatical skills as they can receive feedback on their language use.

Instructional Methods and Strategies for Receptive Grammatical Skills

Instructional methods and strategies play a crucial role in facilitating the formation of receptive grammatical skills. Teachers can use various strategies such as explicit instruction, input enhancement, and corrective feedback to enhance learners' receptive grammatical skills. Explicit instruction involves explicitly teaching learners the grammatical rules and structures of the target language. Input enhancement involves highlighting the target language's grammatical structures in input materials such as texts and videos. Corrective feedback involves providing learners with feedback on their language use, highlighting any errors or inconsistencies in their grammar.

Recommendations for Enhancing Receptive Grammatical Skills

To enhance the formation of receptive grammatical skills, teachers and learners can take various steps. Teachers can use a combination of instructional methods and strategies to facilitate the development of these skills. Additionally, teachers can provide learners with ample opportunities to practice and apply their receptive grammatical skills in real-life situations. Learners can also take steps such as immersing themselves in the target language, seeking feedback from native speakers, and using language learning apps and tools to enhance their receptive grammatical skills.

Conclusion

The formation of receptive grammatical skills is a critical aspect of language acquisition. However, learners often encounter various challenges in developing these skills. Factors such as age, language background, and learning environment can influence the acquisition of receptive grammatical skills. Additionally, instructional methods and strategies play a crucial role in facilitating the development of these skills. To enhance the formation of receptive grammatical skills, teachers and learners can take various steps such as using instructional methods and strategies, providing opportunities for practice, and seeking feedback from native speakers. By taking these steps, learners can overcome the challenges and develop effective receptive grammatical skills.

References:

1. Hoshimova, N. A. (2020). Ingliz va o'zbek tillarining funktsional uslublari. *Молодой ученый*, (19), 584-585.
2. Toirova, N. I. (2019). The significance of the symbols of Mirror and Portrait in teaching Symbolism. *sign*, 1, 22.
3. Mamajanova, M. (2021). MODEL CONCEPT MODELING IN LINGUISTICS TYPES OF LINGUISTIC MODELS. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1), 160-163.
4. Holbekova, M., Mamajanova, M., & Holbekov, S. (2021). COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1), 83-85.
5. Mirzayevna, M. (2021). Innovative technologies in foreign language teaching methodology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(12), 465-467.
6. Kasimova, G. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF ICE BREAKING ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 117-120.
7. Makhmudovna, K. G. (2022). Creative Strategies to Improve Vocabulary Teaching. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 259-261.
8. Kurbanovna E. N. Application of multimedia and interactive materials in foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 2 (147). – С. 65-67.
9. Alimjanova, M. (2023). UTILIZING TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE SKILLS. *Ilm-fan va ta'lim*, 1(5).
10. Akhmedova, M. (2012). Characteristics of bronchial asthma associated with allergic rhinosinusitis in children. *Medical and Health Science Journal*, 11, 39-43.

11. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2022). Developing professional communicative competence of medical students in a foreign language. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 15, 45-50.
12. Isaqjon, T. (2022). Strategies and techniques for improving EFL learners’ reading skills. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(11), 94-99.
13. Mohira, A., & Isakjon, T. (2022). METHODOLOGY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 3, 68-71.
14. Ahundjanova, M. A. (2020). METHODS AND METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE. *Экономика и социум*, (11), 46-49.
15. Ahundjanova, M. (2022). THE NEEDS FOR IMPROVING LEARNERS’AUTONOMY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES–AS A KEY FACTOR TO BOOST LANGUAGE LEARNERS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 390-392.
16. Gafurova, N. I. (2021). Structural-semantic classification of construction terms in English and Uzbek languages. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 571-575.
17. Mirzaaliyev, I., & Oxunov, A. (2021). EKVIVALENTSIZ LEKSIKANING O’ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA IFODALANISHI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 209-212.
18. Oxunov, A. O. O. (2021). INGLIZ VA O’ZBEK TILLARIDA UNDOV SO’ZLAR (INTERJECTION) NING IFODALANISHI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 401-406.
19. Abdukhalimova Sarvinozkhon. (2023). HOZIRGI INGLIZ VA O’ZBEK TILLARIDAGI ZIDLOV BOG‘LANGAN QO‘SHMA GAPLARNING SEMANTIK TAHLILI . *PEDAGOGS Jurnal*, 27(1), 153–157.